

1 **Female-biased dispersal under conditions of low male mating**
2 **competition in a polygynous mammal**

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22 FEMALE-BIASED DISPERSAL IN RED DEER

23

24 **Abstract**

25 Sex-biased dispersal is a common phenomenon in birds and mammals. Competition for mates has
26 been argued to be an important selective pressure favouring dispersal. Sexual differences in the
27 level of intrasexual competition may produce asymmetries in the costs-benefits balance of dispersal
28 and philopatry for males and females, which may favour male-biased dispersal in polygynous
29 species such as most mammals. This being the case, condition-dependent dispersal predicts that
30 male-bias should decrease if mating competition relaxes. We test this expectation for red deer,
31 where male-biased dispersal is the norm. In Southwestern Spain, red deer populations located in
32 non-fenced hunting estates presented altered structures with sex ratio strongly biased to females and
33 high proportion of young males. As a consequence, mate competition in these populations was
34 lower than in other, most typical red deer populations. We found that, under such conditions of
35 altered population structure, dispersal was female- rather than male-biased. Additionally, mate
36 competition positively related to male dispersal but negatively to female dispersal. Other factors
37 such as resource competition, age of individuals and sex ratio were not related to male or female
38 dispersal. Males may not disperse if intrasexual competition is low and then females may disperse
39 as a response to male philopatry. We propose hypotheses related to female mate choice to explain
40 female dispersal under male philopatry. The shift of the sex-biased dispersal pattern along the
41 gradient of mate competition highlights its condition-dependence as well as the interaction between
42 male and female dispersal in the evolution of sex-biased dispersal.

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48 **Introduction**

49 Dispersal from the natal area is a common behaviour in many animals (Clobert et al. 2001).
50 Dispersal strategies can evolve under a large variety of opposing selective pressures. Forces
51 precluding dispersal include mortality risk, familiarity with natal area and benefits of kin
52 cooperation (Greenwood & Harvey 1976; Bengtsson 1978; Johnson & Gaines 1990; Le Gaillard et
53 al. 2006). Selective pressures promoting dispersal include inbreeding avoidance (Packer 1979;
54 Dobson 1982; Pusey 1987; Waser et al. 1986; Clutton-Brock 1989; Wolff 1994; Perrin & Mazalov
55 1999; Lehmann & Perrin 2003; Höner et al. 2007), resource competition (Clarke 1978; Greenwood
56 1980), mate competition (Greenwood 1980; Dobson 1982; Moore & Ali 1984; Wolff 1993) and
57 cooperative behaviour among kin (Perrin & Goudet 2001; Le Gaillard et al. 2006). The balance
58 between selective forces should determine the evolutionary stable patterns of dispersal in each
59 species and sex (Greenwood 1980; Dobson 1982; Lambin et al. 2001, Perrin & Goudet 2001;
60 Lawson Handley & Perrin 2007; Ronce 2007).

61 In most mammals and birds, dispersal follows a sex-biased pattern in which dispersal is
62 mostly carried out by individuals of one sex, either males or females. Inbreeding avoidance is a
63 widely invoked cause for sex-biased dispersal because the dispersal of only one sex is enough to
64 accomplish it (Pusey 1987; Clutton-Brock 1989; Höner et al. 2007). However, inbreeding
65 avoidance only predicts that one of the sexes will disperse while the other sex will remain strictly
66 philopatric (arbitrarily males or females; Perrin & Mazalov 1999). Hence, since which sex will
67 disperse is indifferent for inbreeding avoidance, sex-bias in dispersal behaviour is not predicted by
68 this theory unless some asymmetry exists between the sexes in the intensity of sex-specific
69 pressures for dispersal (Guillaume & Perrin 2006, 2009; Perrin & Mazalov 2000).

70 In mammals, dispersal is normally male-biased (Greenwood 1980; Dobson 1982). Early
71 studies of mammalian dispersal argue that competition for mates may be the most important

72 selective pressure implicated in male-biased dispersal (Greenwood 1980; Dobson 1982). Perrin &
73 Mazalov (2000) used game-theoretical models to conclude that mate competition induces male-
74 biased dispersal, unless resource competition is so high as to promote the dispersal of females.
75 Empirical studies also show that mate competition may be the most common force implicated in
76 male-biased dispersal in mammals (review in Lawson Handley & Perrin 2007).

77 An individual's decision over whether to disperse may depend on its internal, social and
78 environmental conditions (Ims & Hjermann 2001; Ronce 2007; Armsworth 2009). Male dispersal
79 promoted by mate competition may be condition-dependent, so that males may tend to cease
80 dispersal if mate competition relaxes. The lack of dispersal of males may in turn affect dispersal
81 decisions of females, for instance because females might avoid mating with relatives. This would
82 lead to female-biased dispersal if inbreeding is more costly to females than to males (Smith 1979;
83 Parker 1983; Höner et al. 2007; but see Guillaume & Perrin 2009). In some mammalian species
84 where dispersal is female-biased, inbreeding avoidance appears to be the most likely selective
85 pressure causing it (Lawson Handley & Perrin 2007). However, females may avoid mating with
86 relatives and not disperse, thus boosting the dispersal of males who must seek receptive mates at
87 other areas (Lehmann & Perrin 2003; Höner et al. 2007). The study of different populations within
88 a species, may provide the opportunity to explore how social and environmental conditions affect
89 the interacting decisions of each sex over whether to disperse or to stay.

90 The red deer (*Cervus elaphus*) is a polygynous mammal that shows a male-biased dispersal
91 pattern (Darling 1937; Lowe 1966, Clutton-Brock et al. 1982, 2002; Catchpole et al. 2004; Nussey
92 et al. 2005; Frantz et al. 2008). Male dispersal takes place between 2 and 5 years of age. In contrast,
93 females rarely disperse and they form matrilineal groups including socially, spatially and
94 genetically related individuals (Clutton-Brock et al. 1982, 2002; Catchpole et al. 2004). Male-biased
95 dispersal has been found in populations with equilibrated population structures such as in Rum

96 Island (Scotland) (Clutton-Brock et al. 1982, 2002; Catchpole et al. 2004; Nussey et al. 2005) or in
97 Petit Pierre National Reserve (France) (Bonenfant et al. 2004; Frantz et al. 2008). By contrast, in
98 some populations in Southwestern Spain, population structure is very imbalanced. In Spain, red
99 deer populations are mostly located in private hunting estates (typically 750 to 3000 ha). Some of
100 these estates are surrounded by two-metres high mesh fences that prevent deer from entering and
101 leaving the estates. In these fenced estates hunting is moderate and population structure is little
102 altered although individuals cannot disperse due to the fences. Other estates are not fenced but,
103 because animals can move among estates, managers try to hunt all males that they legally can (2
104 years or older), with little culling pressure towards females. Hunting bias towards males generates
105 female-biased sex ratios and male age structures represented only by younger individuals. This
106 altered population structure can reduce male mate competition (Clutton-Brock et al. 1997; Shuster
107 & Wade 2003). Thus, these populations located in non-fenced estates constitute a system that
108 allows testing some predictions on mammalian sex-biased dispersal.

109 In this work we investigate, for red deer populations, whether the pattern of sex-biased
110 dispersal may change under conditions of low male competition for mates. In particular, we explore
111 whether male dispersal decreases when male mate competition relaxes and, this being the case, how
112 females respond. Firstly, we describe population structure and mate competition in populations
113 located in open estates in Spain and compared them with those found in Spanish fenced estates as
114 well as in other European populations (red deer populations of Rum Island (Scotland) and Petit
115 Pierre Reserve (France)). Secondly, we investigate, on the basis of genetic analyses, the sex-biased
116 dispersal pattern in non-fenced red deer populations in Spain. Finally, we explore the role of
117 potential factors that may be implicated in variations in dispersal among our study populations.

118

119 **Material and Methods**

120 *Study area and populations*

121 The study was conducted in Mediterranean ecosystems in Southwestern Spain. Dispersal was
122 studied in 10 red deer populations in a game district called Sierra de San Pedro, in Extremadura
123 region. These populations were within hunting estates that were non-fenced, so that animals could
124 move between them. We also included 2 fenced estates from Sierra de San Pedro, only for
125 population structure and mate competition comparisons (see below). Finally, we also included 2
126 non-fenced estates located in a different game district (Sierra Morena, in Andalucía region) for
127 some genetic structure analyses (see below). All of these estates typically include a part of a
128 mountain range covered by Mediterranean scrub (*Cistus* spp., *Erica* spp., *Genista hirsuta*,
129 *Lavandula* spp.) and forest (*Quercus* spp., *Arbutus unedo*, *Olea europaea*, *Phyllirea* spp.) and a
130 lower and flatter land, covered by open, oak woodland or *dehesa* (*Quercus* spp.).

131

132 *Census data and sample collection*

133 During the peak of rut (September-October 2004), we conducted road-side counts in Sierra de San
134 Pedro estates in which we registered individuals, indicating their sex and estimated age class (for
135 males: yearling, young (2 years old) and adult (3 years old or older)). The counts, which were made
136 at sunset, covered the area of the estates that managers recommended to see the maximum number
137 of individuals. With these counts we established number of females and sex ratio (males/females)
138 for each population (yearling males were excluded from calculations (see e. g. Clutton-Brock et al.
139 1997)). We used the cars of land managers to carry out the road-side counts. Land managers
140 continually perform car journeys within the estates, so animals normally ignored us during data
141 collection. Because of this, counting individuals multiple times was minimized. However, in one
142 population we carried out five different road-side counts during the rutting period (13, 14, 15, 16
143 and 22 of September 2005) in order to see the repeatability of our punctual data collection. The

144 variance and the coefficient of variation in the 5 temporal data was lower than in the 12 spatial data
145 (for instance, number of females observed: mean = 31.00 for temporal data, mean = 116.65 for
146 spatial data; variance = 27.50 for temporal data, variance = 4231.65 for spatial data; coefficient of
147 variation = 16.92 for temporal data, coefficient of variation = 55.90 for spatial data).

148 During the hunting period (October 2004-February 2005) we obtained tissue samples from
149 culled individuals. The hunting procedure was the Spanish *montería* for males or a similar non-
150 selective culling for females. In both cases, packs of dogs were released within a shrub area to move
151 the deer outwards to the sites around where hunters were placed, so it is a little biased procedure to
152 obtain data from culled red deer (see Martínez et al. 2005). This study never provoked hunters to
153 shoot additional deer (see also Carranza et al. 2004).

154 From the 12 populations in Sierra de San Pedro game district we attempted to sample stags,
155 hinds and their foetuses when pregnant. However in one population we did not get pregnant hinds
156 in the sample, so the number of populations was reduced for some analyses. From the 2 populations
157 in Sierra Morena game district we collected samples of culled males and females. From sampled
158 individuals we took a piece of tissue (muscle in most cases) and preserved it frozen at -21 °C.
159 Genomic DNA was purified by proteinase K digestion and salting out procedure (Miller et al. 1988).
160 We extracted the mandible of culled individuals to estimate age by counting cementum growth
161 marks at the interradicular pad under the first molar (Mitchel 1967; Carranza et al. 2004).

162

163 *Habitat quality characterization*

164 Habitat quality characterization was determined to obtain resource competition variables. To
165 determine habitat quality in our Iberian estates, we followed a method broadly used by deer
166 managers in Southwestern Spain. This method applies Hobbs et al. (1982) model to the data
167 contributed by Rodríguez-Berrocal (1978, 1979) for Mediterranean ecosystems (Caballero 1985).

168 Managers use information in Table 1 to estimate the habitat quality and the carrying capacity of
169 estates. The values are referred to summer season. Summer is the period of scarcity in
170 Mediterranean ecosystems and food availability at this moment mostly determines quality and
171 carrying capacity in these habitats (see e.g. Bugalho & Milne 2003). Habitat types and values in
172 table 1 offer a reliable relative habitat quality in estates of Southwestern Spain (Torres-Porras,
173 Carranza & Pérez-González, unpublished data). The Mediterranean forest is a very diverse forest
174 that includes many species of trees and scrubs; *noble* scrub is a climacic forest normally located in
175 shady faces of the mountains; serial *jaral* is constituted by low consumable scrubs of genus *Cistus*,
176 *Lavandula* and *Genista*; *Pinus* reforestations are normally composed of *Pinus pinaster* and *Pinus*
177 *pinea*; *dehesas* are flatter lands covered by open oak woodland; crops are normally cereals such as
178 oat, barley or wheat. In order to locate each habitat type in all of the estates, we mapped in Arc
179 View 3.2 (Esri, 2006) areas of *dehesa*, crops, *Pinus* reforestation and forest with the help of aerial
180 ortophotos. To differentiate Mediterranean forest, *noble* scrub and serial *jaral* we visited the estates
181 (February-August 2004) and with the help of maps and GPS we determined the distribution of each
182 forest type. In these visits we determined the existence of unproductive areas and confirmed the
183 distribution of each habitat type. With data in Table 1 and the area of each habitat type we
184 determined parameters such as biomass per hectare (*biomass*), energy per hectare (*energy*), and
185 nitrogen per hectare (*nitrogen*). All of these parameters measured habitat quality associated to each
186 estate. In our study area, these three variables are highly correlated (*biomass-energy*: Spearman, N
187 = 10, $r = 0.975$, $p < 0.001$; *biomass-nitrogen*: Spearman, N = 10, $r = 0.854$, $p = 0.002$; *energy-*
188 *nitrogen*: Spearman, N = 10, $r = 0.830$, $p = 0.003$), so any of them can be considered as a habitat
189 quality estimation. Habitat quality determination took place during the summer (June-August of
190 2004).

191

192 *Microsatellite genotyping*

193 We typed individuals at 12 microsatellite loci: OarFCB193, OarCP26, OarFCB304, CelJP38,
194 CelJP15, TGLA94, TGLA53, BM1818, CSSM22, CSSM66, ILSTS06, CSPA115 (Coulson et al.
195 1998; Marshall et al. 1998; Bonnet et al. 2002; Martínez et al. 2002; Kuehn et al. 2003). After
196 polymerase chain reaction we used ABI3130 DNA sequencer and GENEMAPPER software
197 (Applied Biosystems, New Jersey, USA) to determine allele sizes. We combined the markers in 5
198 multiplex or simplex PCRs (1x6, 1x3 and 3x1; number of PCRs x number of markers). For simplex
199 PCRs, polymerase chain reactions were carried out on volumes of 10 μ L with approximately 50-
200 100 ng of genomic DNA, 0.25 units of *Taq* polymerase (Advanced Biotechnologies, Surrey, United
201 Kingdom), 1 μ L of each primer, 1.5 mM MgCL₂ and 0.2mM dNTPs in the manufactured's buffer.
202 These conditions were used as a first step to multiplex PCR development. Later on, different PCR
203 reagent concentrations, such as DNA template, MgCL₂, *Taq* polymerase and primers mix, were
204 tested (Fernández-García et al. in preparation). To assess the accuracy of genotyping, 60 individuals
205 were retyped, and returned identical genotypes. These retyped individuals included males, females
206 and foetuses, and belonged to our sample stock (many of them included in this work). Retyped
207 individuals were selected from those individuals without missing genotypes. Tests for linkage
208 disequilibrium were performed by exact tests based on Markov chain method as implemented by
209 GENEPOP 3.4 (Raymond & Rousset 1995). No loci pair showed significant linkage disequilibrium.

210

211 *Mate competition determination*

212 We determined mate competition for the 12 populations (10 non-fenced and 2 fenced) located in
213 Sierra de San Pedro game district. To quantify the level of mate competition for each population we
214 firstly determined the most probable number of fathers that explained the set of foetuses sampled in
215 each population. It was unlikely that most of the actual fathers of the foetuses sampled in each

216 population were included among the sampled males in that population, so paternity inference
217 methods based on likelihood (Marshall et al. 1998) were inappropriate. As an alternative, we
218 applied a method proposed to infer the probable number of fathers in wild populations with
219 polyandrous mating system (Bretman & Tregenza 2004). We proceeded by comparing mothers'
220 genotypes with the genotypes of their foetuses to identify by exclusion the paternally inherited
221 genotype. For homozygous foetuses, the same genotype was inherited from mother and father.
222 There were 13% cases of ambiguity (i. e. foetus and mother shared the same heterozygous
223 genotype). In these cases, we eliminated the foetus genotype for the locus in which ambiguity
224 occurred. Paternal genotypes were used to infer the number of fathers that sired a sample of
225 foetuses in each population. The number of different alleles from the locus with more paternal
226 alleles divided by 2 (each father could potentially contribute two different alleles) gives an estimate
227 of the minimum number of fathers in each population. However, this is a very simplistic and
228 conservative method for inferring the number of fathers (Bretman & Tregenza 2004). So we applied
229 a method which uses the frequency of alleles in the populations and which is implemented by
230 PARENTAGE software (Emery et al. 2001). PARENTAGE uses a combination of Markov chain
231 Monte-Carlo techniques to select the most probable set of fathers from the distribution of parents
232 and sibling relationships that could have produced the observed sample. Runs for each population
233 contained 5,000 samples with a burn-in of 5,000 and a thinning interval of 400 (the actual number
234 of MCMC steps was $5,000 \times 400 = 2,000,000$). We used four additional metropolis-coupled chains
235 with different posterior densities to favour mixing for the chains. We used as number of fathers the
236 mean number of fathers obtained in the 5,000 samples (see a more detailed description of the
237 method in Supporting Material).

238 Once we had estimated the observed number of fathers that explained the set of foetuses in
239 each estate, we calculated the number of fathers expected under random mating for this number of

240 foetuses. Then, for each estate we created a simulated situation in which we had a number of
241 females that mated with males; there was random mating so males had the same probability to mate.
242 Mating distribution depended on population sex ratio. We randomly chose sets of females with
243 different sample sizes (1-20) and counted the number of males (fathers) who had mated with each
244 sample of females. The resulting regression equation between number of sampled females and
245 fathers obtained in simulations, together with the actual sample size collected in each population (x
246 in the equation), were used to estimate the expected number of fathers in each estate (y in the
247 equation) with this sample size (x in the equation) and sex ratio. The number of females used in the
248 simulations, the female reference population, was obtained by correcting census data by the
249 proportion of pregnant females (0.78 in our populations (Pérez-González et al. 2009)). We obtained
250 on average 78.87 ± 29.32 (mean \pm standard deviation) pregnant females per rutting area, so we used
251 79 females for simulations. To see the influence of this decision on the results, we remade the
252 analyses with female population size equal to 50 and equal to 108 (79 ± 29). The results were very
253 similar using 50, 79 and 108 females, so variations in female population size had little effect in
254 simulation results.

255 For each population we calculated mate competition as F_e/F_o , F_e being the expected number
256 of fathers in the population under random mating, and F_o the observed number of fathers in this
257 population. In populations with sex ratio biased to females, under random mating, $F_e = F_o$, so mate
258 competition equals 1.

259 Genetic estimates of mate competition were obtained from relatively small sample sizes of
260 mother-foetus pairs per estate. To prevent any strong influence of small sample sizes on the results,
261 we also used the proportion of adult males as an estimate of mate competition (Gibson & Guinness
262 1980; Clutton-Brock et al. 1997). Proportion of adult males was the number of males ≥ 3 years old
263 with respect to total number of males ≥ 2 years old. Data on the number of adult and young males

264 were obtained from culled individuals in non-fenced estates, where hunters are allowed to shoot
265 every male two years old or older so that we were confident that all ages (≥ 2 years) were equally
266 sampled. In fenced estates, however, hunters have fixed quotas that limited the maximum number
267 of stags they can shoot, so older ages are overrepresented with respect to younger ones. So for
268 fenced estates we used the age-class estimations from census data to obtain the proportion of adult
269 males. This estimation was only used to compare population conditions with respect to non-fenced
270 estates, but indeed dispersal was only studied in non-fenced estates. The results on the relationship
271 between mate competition and dispersal were consistent by using either of both estimates of male
272 mate competition (genetically estimated mate competition and proportion of adult males) (see
273 results for proportion of adult males as mate competition measure in Supporting Material).

274

275 *Genetic structure and dispersal pattern*

276 Sex-biased dispersal has consequences on the genetic structure of populations (Chesser 1991; Aars
277 & Ims 2000; Clobert et al. 2001; Prugnolle & de Meeus 2002). Dispersal plays a major role in
278 genetic structure by acting as a homogenizing force that maintains genetic cohesion and similarity
279 among populations (Slatkin 1987). This genetic cohesion among populations will be maintained by
280 the dispersing sex, so genetic structure will be established mainly by the philopatric sex (Mossman
281 & Waser 1999). As a consequence, at a local scale, pairwise genetic relationship between
282 individuals of the philopatric sex should be stronger than between individuals of the dispersing sex.
283 As spatial distance between individual pairs increases, the genetic relationship between individuals
284 of the philopatric sex decreases, while in the dispersing sex this decrease does not occur, or it
285 occurs with lower intensity (Nussey et al. 2005; Coulon et al. 2006).

286 Before establishing the dispersal pattern, it was necessary to determine if populations
287 constituted a metapopulation within which all of them were genetically interconnected. We used

288 STRUCTURE 2.0 (Pritchard et al. 2000) to identify the metapopulations in our study area. This
289 program uses Bayesian methodology to determine the level of genetic substructure in the data set
290 independently of sampling areas. To determine the number of genetic clusters (K), 5 independent
291 runs of $K = 1-12$ were carried out with 100,000 iterations, following a burn-in period of 10,000
292 iterations. We assumed admixture and a correlation among genetic frequencies. We used an *ad hoc*
293 statistic ΔK to identify the true number of genetic clusters (K) (Evanno et al. 2005). The 5 runs of
294 the true K value were averaged using CLUMPP version 1.1.1 (Jakobsson & Rosenberg 2007) and
295 displayed by DISTRUCT version 1.1 (Rosenberg 2004). After a first run that identified the major
296 genetic discontinuities, we made second runs separately with each genetic group obtained in the
297 first run. Thus we looked for minor genetic discontinuities within major genetic areas. If the
298 obtained genetic cluster had geographic identity, we regarded it as a metapopulation composed of a
299 set of populations. Should several metapopulations be obtained, and to determine if there was actual
300 exchange of individuals among metapopulations, we used another Bayesian methodology
301 implemented by BAYESASS (Wilson & Rannala 2003) with 3,000,000 MCMC repetitions and a
302 burn-in period of 1,000,000. This methodology assumes relatively low levels of gene flow between
303 metapopulations and the proportion of immigrant individuals in a metapopulation may be lower
304 than a third of the population per generation. To assess the convergence of MCMC several runs
305 were carried out by changing initial values of migration rate and inbreeding coefficient. For
306 STRUCTURE and BAYESASS analyses we used the 10 non-fenced populations of Sierra de San
307 Pedro and the 2 non-fenced populations of Sierra Morena. We included the populations from Sierra
308 Morena to ensure that dispersal did not occur at a geographical scale bigger than the distance among
309 Sierra de San Pedro populations.

310 To assess differences between the sexes in intra-metapopulation genetic structure, we made
311 several approximations based on instantaneous dispersal (Goudet et al. 2002; Prugnolle & de Meeus

312 2002; Lawson Handley & Perrin 2007). Firstly, we established genetic structure at the level of F_{st}
313 values which indicate genetic differentiation between populations (Wright 1965). Thus we
314 quantified global F_{st} by using only males and compared it with that obtained by using only females.
315 Also pairwise F_{st} between populations were obtained by analysing males and females separately.
316 Significant departures of F_{st} from 0 were assessed by 10,000 permutations. Analyses of F_{st} and
317 permutations were carried out with GENETIX 4.02 (Belkhir et al. 2001). Another method to assess
318 sex differences in genetic structure is the comparison of geographical distances and genetic
319 relatedness between pairs of individuals (Prugnolle & de Meeus 2002; Nussey et al. 2005; Coulon
320 et al. 2006). We considered as the geographic location of individuals the mean point of the estates
321 in which they were sampled. As in Nussey et al. (2005) and to allow comparison between studies,
322 genetic relatedness coefficients (Lynch & Ritland 1999) and geographical distances between pairs
323 of individuals were examined by using SPAGEDI software (Hardy & Vekemans 2002). Average
324 estimates were taken for pairs of individuals separated by distance intervals of 5 Km. Thus, we
325 established 8 distance intervals: 0 (the same estate), < 5, < 10, < 15, < 20, < 25, < 30 and < 35 Km.
326 To assess whether the degree of genetic relatedness between individuals depended on the
327 geographic distance, we carried out permutation tests implemented with SPAGEDI. In these
328 permutations, the spatial group (estates) locations were permuted among the available locations to
329 test the regression slope. We used 10,000 permutations. The analysis was conducted separately for
330 pairs of males and pairs of females.

331

332 *Statistical model for sex-biased dispersal*

333 The comparison between male and female parameters (such as pairwise genetic relatedness) raises a
334 statistical problem of pseudoreplication (Prugnolle & de Meeus 2002). To account for this problem,
335 we followed Knight et al. (1999) who proposed a separate regression between geographic distance

336 and genetic relatedness for each individual (see also Prugnolle & de Meeus 2002). Here males and
337 females were also treated separately. The slopes of all these individual regressions can be compared
338 between sexes to determine sex-biased dispersal pattern. Also, this variable allowed us to assess
339 sex-biased dispersal hypotheses which could be implicated in red deer dispersal. For that we made a
340 Mixed Model (REML: SPSS software vs. 13, SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL U.S.A.) with the slopes of
341 individual regressions as dependent variables, sex as a factor and the following covariates: male
342 mate competition, female resource competition and sex ratio of the population to which individuals
343 belong, and age of individuals.

344 We used two estimates of male mate competition: genetically estimated mate competition
345 and proportion of adult males (see above). Here we only present the model for genetically estimated
346 mate competition using PARENTAGE software, although the models were similar by using either
347 mate competition estimate (see model for proportion of adult males in Supporting Material). We
348 used 3 variables to estimate resource competition by females: number of females (*females*), *biomass*
349 and *biomass/females* (see above). Here we only present the model for *biomass/females*, although the
350 models were similar when we used any female resource competition measure (see models for the
351 remaining measurements in Supporting Material). We included population sex ratio to control for
352 its possible effect on sex-biased dispersal (see e.g. Juillard 2000; Leturque & Rousset 2003). We
353 included age of individuals to control for any effect of age-dependent dispersal (Clutton-Brock et al.
354 1982; Vitalis 2002; Broquet et al. 2009). We ran initially a full factorial analysis and afterwards the
355 non-significant interactions were removed by using a backward stepwise procedure.

356

357 *Sample sizes for analyses*

358 Table 2 shows the number of culled individuals which were used in the analyses.

359

360 **Results**

361 *Characteristics of red deer populations*

362 Population structure differed significantly between non-fenced and fenced estates in Sierra de San
 363 Pedro: sex ratio (males/females) and proportion of adult males (Fig. 1; Mann-Whitney U test: N
 364 $_{(\text{non-fenced})} = 10$, $N_{(\text{fenced})} = 2$, $Z = -2.148$, $P = 0.032$, for sex ratio; $N_{(\text{non-fenced})} = 10$, $N_{(\text{fenced})} = 2$, $Z = -$
 365 1.933 , $P = 0.05$, for proportion of adult males). However, the genetic estimate of male mate
 366 competition was variable among populations and did not significantly differ between non-fenced
 367 and fenced estates (Fig. 1; Mann-Whitney U test: $N_{(\text{non-fenced})} = 9$, $N_{(\text{fenced})} = 2$, $Z = -0.943$, $P =$
 368 0.345).

369

370 *Genetic structure and sex-biased dispersal pattern*

371 Bayesian methodology implemented by STRUCTURE showed that $K = 2$ was the most probable
 372 number of metapopulations (Fig. 2a). Plotting individual probabilities for each K value (Fig. 2b)
 373 revealed two population sets, one of them including Sierra de San Pedro populations (SP) and the
 374 other including Sierra Morena populations (SH; Fig. 3). The membership coefficient of probability
 375 (q) was not different between sexes (Mixed Model (REML) with metapopulations as random factor:
 376 factor sex: $F_{1,380} = 0.725$, $P = 0.395$; random factor: variance \pm SE = 0.442 ± 0.625 , Wald $Z = 0.707$,
 377 $P = 0.480$). In the second run using open estates from Sierra de San Pedro district, ΔK was
 378 maximized in $K = 2$ (Fig. 2c). Plotting individual probabilities for each K value (Fig. 2d) revealed
 379 two population sets (metapopulations): SP1 in centre-east of Sierra de San Pedro and SP2 in the
 380 west (Fig. 3). The membership coefficient of probability (q) was not different between sexes
 381 (Mixed Model (REML) with metapopulations as random factor: factor sex: $F_{1,307} = 0.910$, $P = 0.341$;
 382 random factor: variance \pm SE = 0.320 ± 0.454 , Wald $Z = 0.706$, $P = 0.480$).

383 BAYESASS results indicated that there was very little individual exchange among
384 metapopulations. Thus, 87% of the females and 82% of males had more than 0.95 probability of
385 neither they nor their parents being immigrants coming from any other population set. Resultant
386 migration rates among the metapopulations were very low (Table 3). Then SP1, SP2 and SH can be
387 regarded as metapopulations with little genetic connection.

388 Due to the low number of estates sampled in SP2 and SH (2 estates in each of them),
389 intrametapopulation sex-biased dispersal pattern was analyzed only for the estates of SP1 (8
390 populations, but 7 with genetically estimated male mate competition). By using only males, global
391 F_{st} obtained was 0.0164, it being significantly higher than 0 (10,000 permutations, $P < 0.05$). For
392 females, global F_{st} was 0.0055, it being non-significantly different from 0 (10,000 permutations,
393 $P > 0.05$). Pairwise F_{st} values were significantly higher for males than for females (Wilcoxon
394 matched pairs test, $N = 28$, $Z = 2.824$, $P = 0.005$). Likewise, the number of significantly higher than
395 0 pairwise F_{st} was 9 pairs for males (32.14 % of pairs) and 4 pairs for females (14.28 % of pairs)
396 (Table 4).

397 Genetic relatedness (R) between pairs of females did not significantly change throughout the
398 range of distances (10,000 permutations, $P = 0.111$). Linear regression of mean R against distance
399 between pairs of females showed a slight decline in relatedness with geographic distance (intercept
400 \pm SE = 0.008 ± 0.003 , slope \pm ES = -0.002 ± 0.001 , $r^2 = 0.670$, $P = 0.013$, Fig. 4). However, genetic
401 relatedness between pairs of males changed (declined) with geographic distance (10,000
402 permutations, $P = 0.002$). Within the same estate (distance = 0), relatedness between males
403 averaged R = 0.021, while it approached 0 at around 15 Km geographic distance (Fig. 4). Linear
404 regression showed that mean R between pairs of males strongly declined with geographic distance
405 (intercept \pm SE = 0.021 ± 0.004 , slope \pm ES = -0.006 ± 0.001 , $r^2 = 0.898$, $P < 0.001$, Fig. 4).

406

407 *Model for sex-biased dispersal*

408 Individual dispersal, measured as the slope of the relationship between its geographic distance and
409 genetic relatedness with the remaining individuals of the same sex in the seven studied populations
410 of SP1, was higher for females than for males (see Sex in Table 5). The remaining factors (male
411 mate competition (genetically estimated), female resource competition (*biomass / females*), sex
412 ratio in the population and age of individuals) resulted non-significant in the model (Table 5).
413 However, there was a highly significant interaction between sex and male mate competition: male
414 dispersal significantly increased with mate competition (estimate slope \pm SE = 0.0063 ± 0.0029 , t_{201}
415 = 2.172, $P = 0.031$) while female dispersal significantly decreased with mate competition (estimate
416 slope \pm SE = -0.0062 ± 0.0028 , $t_{201} = -2.215$, $P = 0.028$) (Table 5; Fig. 5).

417

418 **Discussion**

419 Our results show, for the studied red deer populations, a female-biased dispersal pattern that
420 associated with conditions of low mate competition among males. Our studied non-fenced red deer
421 populations provide a study case where male mate competition tends in general to be low as a
422 consequence of altered population structure. On one hand they have sex ratios strongly biased to
423 females. Although sex ratio in sexually dimorphic species such as red deer tends to be biased to
424 females (Fisher 1930), the observed sex ratios in our non-fenced populations were highly skewed to
425 females compared with fenced populations or with other red deer populations. For example, for red
426 deer in Rum Island (Scotland), between 1957 and 1980 the sex ratio (stags/hinds) was 0.89 ± 0.10
427 (mean \pm standard deviation) (Clutton-Brock et al. 1982). Also, in Petite Pierre National Reserve
428 (France), the sex ratio (adult males/(adult males+adult females)) ranged from 0.4 to 0.65
429 (Bonenfant et al. 2004). Sex ratio is an important parameter for mate competition and the
430 opportunity for sexual selection (Reynolds 1996; Shuster & Wade 2003).

431 On the other hand, the proportion of adult males (3 years old or older) tended to be low in
432 non-fenced populations (Fig. 1). Red deer males do not reach social maturity until 5-7 years old
433 (Clutton-Brock & Albon 1989). Young males are not able to efficiently perform many mating
434 behaviours (Ozoga & Verme 1985), so mainly adult males (4-5 years or more) accomplish sexual
435 display and mate competition. Our fenced estates as well as other studied red deer populations
436 presented more equilibrated male age structures (Fig. 1; Clutton-Brock et al. 1982; Bonenfant et al.
437 2004).

438 Individual flow among metapopulations was low and not sex-biased. For genetically
439 interconnected populations, we found that dispersal was female-biased. The female-biased pattern
440 resulted from population-related genetic information such as F_{st} values, and individual-related
441 genetic information such as relatedness. In spite of the difference in scales, these results are
442 contrary to those obtained by Nussey et al. (2005) and by Frantz et al. (2008), who found male-
443 biased dispersal in red deer populations inhabiting the Rum Island (Scotland) and the Petite Pierre
444 National Reserve (France), respectively. Moreover, within our populations, there was a shift from
445 female-biased to male-biased dispersal as male mate competition increased. Other variables such as
446 female resource competition, sex ratio and age of individuals did not associate with sex-biased
447 dispersal.

448 Why males do not disperse? Altered population structures may affect male dispersal through
449 low male mate competition (Dobson 1982; Moore & Ali 1984; Wolff 1993; Perrin & Mazalov
450 2000). In less-altered red deer populations (Nussey et al. 2005; Frantz et al. 2008) male-biased
451 dispersal may be presumably related to mate competition. This situation also appears to occur in
452 some of our study non-fenced populations, but as mate competition decreases, pressure towards
453 male dispersal may relax. For comparison purposes, we have estimated male mate competition in
454 the North Block of Rum (1978 to 1980 data) to be 1.70 ± 0.14 . These values were obtained by using

455 the number of reproducing males (F_o) (Nussey et al. 2005), the number of calves and the sex ratio
456 (Clutton-Brock et al. 1982). Note that this value of mate competition is bigger than the average
457 value found in non-fenced Spanish estates, although within its range of variation. So, like in Rum
458 population, our populations with comparable levels of male mate competition show male-biased
459 dispersal in contrast with those with competition figures below ca. 1.4 that show female-biased
460 dispersal (see Fig. 5).

461 Alternatively to mate competition, males may not disperse because they are younger in our
462 non-fenced populations than in other red deer populations, and dispersal may increase with age at
463 least up to five years old (Clutton-Brock et al. 1982, 2002; Catchpole et al. 2004). However, we
464 found no relationship between age (or its interaction with sex) and dispersal. Likewise, we found no
465 relationship between sex ratio (or its interaction with sex) and dispersal. Therefore, we conclude
466 that, in our populations, male mate competition had a stronger influence than age of individuals or
467 population sex ratio to promote male dispersal.

468 Effects of competition on individuals' decisions to disperse can be divided in competition
469 with conspecific (demographical competition) and competition with relatives (local or kin
470 competition) (Lambin et al. 2001; Ronce 2007). Distinguishing between the effects of demographic
471 and local competition on dispersal is often not obvious whenever population demography is
472 correlated with local genetic relatedness (Ronce 2007). However, Lambin et al. (2001) infer that
473 competition is demographical when the individual's decision to disperse depends on population
474 level traits, while competition is local when this decision depends upon the individual's close
475 environment. Since mate competition is a population level trait, male dispersal may be due to a
476 demographical rather than a local mate competition effect (Lambin et al. 2001). In this sense, at
477 least in some mammals, early exposure to testosterone in males constitutes a proximate factor to

478 their dispersal (Dufty & Belthoff 2001), and the amount of testosterone an individual receives
479 should depend on the mate competition level in its population (Wyatt 2003).

480 An alternative explanation to reduced male dispersal in our populations might be related to
481 male territoriality. Red deer stags normally use harem defence as mating strategy (Clutton-Brock et
482 al. 1982). However, in Iberian populations, because of the scarcity of resources during the rutting
483 period, males also use the defence of mating territories (Carranza et al. 1990). Territoriality is one
484 of the postulated pressures to male philopatry (Greenwood 1980). However, in Iberian red deer
485 populations with non-altered population structures, the range of movements and local dispersal is
486 higher for males than for females (Carranza et al. 1991; Lazo et al. 1994). Furthermore, the
487 advantage of male philopatry when they defend territories is achieved because of their knowledge
488 of the area (Greenwood 1980). In Iberian red deer, males defend small patches of land (around 2 ha)
489 only during a few days of the year (Carranza et al. 1990). In this context, we think that the female-
490 biased dispersal found in our study populations should be due to altered population structures rather
491 than to male territoriality, although we cannot discard some role of mating territoriality to influence
492 the dispersal decisions of some individual males within either pattern of male- or female-biased
493 dispersal.

494 Why do females disperse? We found no significant effect of female resource competition on
495 female dispersal (neither the effect of resource competition nor its interaction with sex were
496 significant). By contrast, female dispersal was related with male mate competition (lower female
497 dispersal as mate competition increased). Since male mate competition has been described as a
498 selective pressure only related to male dispersal, female dispersal should be a response to male
499 philopatry. Two selective pressures might influence female dispersal depending on the relative
500 importance of inbreeding for males and females.

501 First, females might incur higher costs from breeding with relatives than males (Smith 1979;
502 Parker 1983; Höner et al. 2007). So, under low male dispersal, females should disperse to avoid
503 inbreeding (Packer 1979; Pusey 1987; Waser et al. 1986; Clutton-Brock 1989; Wolff 1994; Perrin
504 & Mazalov 1999). There is evidence that matings in our study populations tend to occur between
505 genetically dissimilar mates (Carranza et al., submitted manuscript). Also, there are evidences of
506 inbreeding depression in our populations (Pérez-González et al., submitted manuscript) as well as in
507 other red deer populations (e. g. Coulson et al. 1998, 1999; Slate et al. 2000). In polygynous
508 mammalian species, inbreeding avoidance may induce females to expel males (Lehmann & Perrin
509 2003), or to disperse in order to avoid mating with their fathers when male tenure exceeds female
510 age at first conception (Clutton-Brock 1989). Note that, because females would mate with their sons
511 (since male age structure is biased to young males), the results found in this work may represent a
512 variant of female dispersal to avoid mating with high tenure fathers (Clutton-Brock 1989).

513 Second, females might not incur higher cost from breeding with relatives than males. In this
514 case, inbreeding avoidance may lead to a balanced dispersal strategy (Guillaume & Perrin 2009).
515 This being the case, there should be another selective pressure different from inbreeding avoidance
516 to boost female dispersal in conditions of low male mate competition. One possibility is that in
517 populations with low male mate competition (and low male dispersal), females might disperse to
518 chose high quality males who may provide additive genetic benefits to offspring (Andersson 1994;
519 Mays & Hill 2004). However, we have no evidence so far for female dispersal to areas with most
520 competitive males.

521 To our knowledge this is the first study to show female-biased dispersal in cervids (see for
522 example Darling (1937), Lowe (1966), Nussey et al. (2005) and Frantz et al. (2008) for red deer
523 *Cervus elaphus*; Coulon et al. (2006) for roe deer *Capreolus capreolus*; Nelson (1993) for white-
524 tailed deer *Odocoileus virginianus*; Cederlund & Sand (1992) for moose *Alces alces*; or Robinette

525 (1966) for mule deer *Odocoileus hemionus*). However, some cases have been observed of female-
526 biased dispersal in other groups of mammals; such as horses *Equus caballus* (Monard & Duncan
527 1996), African wild dogs *Lycaon pictus* (Frame & Frame 1976), chimpanzees *Pan troglodytes*
528 (Pusey & Packer 1987), shrews *Crocidura russula* (Favre et al. 1997), bats *Saccopterix bilineata*
529 (Nagy et al. 2007) or wombats *Vombatus ursinus* (Skerratt et al. 2004). In these studies, several
530 selective pressures have been proposed to promote female-biased dispersal: inbreeding avoidance,
531 resource competition, cooperation, resource defence and resource enhancement (reviewed in
532 Lawson Handley & Perrin 2007). Our results suggest a scenario that deserves further empirical and
533 theoretical research, in which males and females interact under the particular conditions of
534 populations with altered structure, highlighting the evolutionary stable responses of each sex to the
535 dispersal behaviour of the other sex, with mate competition and female mating preferences as the
536 most likely determinants of individual decisions (Greenwood 1980; Lambin et al. 2001; Perrin &
537 Goudet 2001; Lawson Handley & Perrin 2007).

538

539

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784 **Figure Legends:**

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786 **Figure 1.** Population structure and mate competition in fenced and non-fenced estates of Sierra de
787 San Pedro. Figure shows mean \pm SE of sex ratio, proportion of adult males and genetically
788 estimated mate competition.

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790 **Figure 2.** Structure software results. a) Log-likelihood values (5 independent runs), $Ln Pr(X/K)$ and
791 *Ad hoc* statistic ΔK that shows the most probable number of genetic clusters (K) for all non-fenced
792 populations. $K = 2$ is the true number of genetic clusters which corresponded with both game
793 districts (Sierra de San Pedro and Sierra Morena). b) Membership coefficient of probability for $K =$
794 2 for all non-fenced populations. Each individual is represented by a thin line, which is portioned
795 into 2 segments with different grey intensity representing the individual's estimated membership
796 fraction in K cluster. Codes represent populations (2 first letters) and sex of individuals (last letter:
797 F (females) and M (males)). c and d) Results for Sierra San Pedro populations.

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799 **Figure 3.** Study area and populations (estates) included in each metapopulation obtained by
800 STRUCTURE. a) Sierra de San Pedro game district. b) Sierra Morena game district. Black estates
801 represent fenced estates.

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803 **Figure 4.** Relationships between geographical distance and genetic relatedness for males (grey
804 circles) and females (white circles). Figure shows means and standard errors.

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806 **Figure 5.** Relationship between male mate competition and dispersal for males and females.

807 Dispersal was measured as the slopes of the individual regressions between geographic distance and

808 genetic relatedness (distance-R slopes). Male mate competition positively related to dispersal in the
809 case of males and negatively in the case of females.
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812 Table 1. Biomass, energy and nitrogen valuation for each habitat type. DM: dry matter; g: grams;

813 Kc: kilocalories; ha: hectare.

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Habitat type	Biomass (Kg DM / ha)	Energy (Kc / Kg DM)	Nitrogen (g / Kg DM)
Mediterranean forest	300	2000	9.8
<i>Noble scrub</i>	300	1800	12.9
<i>Serial jaral</i>	200	1200	9.5
<i>Dehesa</i>	250	1200	10.2
<i>Pinus</i> reforestation	100	1100	9.5
Crops	450	3500	10.2

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831 Table 2. Number of individuals sampled and included in the analyses.

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Individuals	Total	SP	SH	SP non-fenced	SP fenced	SP1 non-fenced	SP2 non-fenced	SP1 non-fenced with fetuses
Total males	390	357	33	307 (a)	54	234	73	181
Total females	241	201	40	161	40	134	27	113
Total fetuses	166	166	0	126	40	102	24	102
Genotyped males	182	180	33 (b)	149 (b)	31	120 (c)	29	101 (d)
Genotyped females	241	201	40(b)	161 (b)	40	134 (c)	27	113 (d)
Genotyped fetuses	166	166	0	126	40	102	24	102 (d)

833 ^a Individuals used to male age structure comparisons.834 ^b Individuals used to STRUCTURE-BAYEASS analyses.835 ^c Individuals used to intrametapopulations genetic structure analysis.836 ^d Individuals used to obtain the model for sex-biased dispersal.

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849 Table 3. BAYESASS results that show migration rate between metapopulations. Listed in rows are
850 the metapopulation into which individuals are migrating, while the origins of the migrants are listed
851 in the columns.

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	SP1	SP2	SH
SP1	0.9946	0.0028	0.0025
SP2	0.0761	0.9161	0.0078
SH	0.0060	0.0034	0.9906

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873 Table 4. Pairwise F_{st} values for pairs of populations from SP1 metapopulation. Pairwise F_{st} values
 874 by using only males are below the diagonal and by using only females are above the diagonal. *
 875 Pairwise F_{st} value significantly higher than 0.

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	AC	CG	CL	CN	ML	MR	MO	VA
AC		0.013	0.006	0.025*	0.002	0.009	0.010	0.012
CG	0.045*		0.006	0.002	0.008	0.007	0.017	0.026*
CL	0.011	0.019		0.010	-0.000	0.006	0.008	0.027*
CN	0.042*	0.006	0.037*		0.008	-0.013	0.009	0.010
ML	0.018	0.007	0.014	0.020		-0.005	0.005	0.014
MR	0.009	0.007	0.029	0.013	-0.015		0.019	-0.006
MO	0.004	0.019*	0.014	0.021*	0.011	0.005		0.022*
VA	0.044*	0.023*	0.014	0.034*	-0.002	0.014	0.032*	

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891 Table 5. Model for sex-biased dispersal. Effect of individual and population variables on dispersal
 892 for males and females (REML procedure). Dispersal was measured as the slopes of the individual
 893 regressions between geographic distance and genetic relatedness (distance-R slopes). Table shows
 894 the estimate differences and standard errors, as well as the results of the model. Males are taken as
 895 reference values for factor sex and its interactions.

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	Estimate (SE)	d.f.	F	P
Intercept	-0.012 (0.006)	1,201	0.308	0.580
Sex	0.017 (0.005)	1,201	10.639	0.001
Age of individuals	0.00009 (0.0002)	1,201	0.156	0.693
Sex ratio	-0.007 (0.019)	1,201	0.129	0.720
Female resource competition	0.0001 (0.0002)	1,201	0.360	0.544
Male mate competition	0.006 (0.003)	1,201	0.000	0.982
Sex*Male mate competition	-0.012 (0.004)	1,201	10.679	0.001

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910 Figure 1

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1031 Figure 5

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